

Review Article

Dual Functional Drug Eluting Dental Implants (DEIs) for Infection Prevention

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Microorganisms present in biofilm around dental implants induce peri-implantitis, a common post-operative complication. Peri-implant infections are caused by a variety of reasons, including the patient's systemic state, the environment, and surgical variables. However, peri-implantitis therapy remains difficult for clinicians, with results that aren't always predictable. As a result, using drug eluting dental implants (DEIs) to prevent peri-implant infections could be a viable option. This review focuses on the challenges associated with peri-implant infections, as well as the use of diverse biomaterials as surface coatings for DEIs, including bioactive materials, antimicrobials, non-antimicrobial medicines, and metals. The use of antibacterial and bioactive coatings has been recommended as a way to lower the rate of infection and inflammation-related dental implant failure.

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Introduction

In recent years, dental implants have been hailed as the optimum option for replacing lost teeth, and their effectiveness is often dependent on the tooth's direct and intimate contact with the implant surface [1-3]. Nonetheless dental implants are affected by a variety of factors, including low bone quality and volume, periodontitis, poor systemic health, cigarette use, and poor oral hygiene. However, the texture, shape, and material of the implant's surface are also critical for osseointegration. Peri-implant infections, also known as peri-implantitis, are a frequent post-operative complication caused by bacterial adherence to the implant surface as a result of the creation of biofilms around the implant [4-6]. Depending on the implant design, size, type of implant, and patient-related variables, the incidence of peri-implantitis ranges from 5 to 20%.

Despite breakthroughs in antibiotics and new operating methods, peri-implantitis care remains difficult because to its high technical and financial demands [7]. As a result, taking proper precautions to avoid peri-implant infections is more important than treating the infection. Though systemic antibiotics are frequently prescribed for the prevention or treatment of peri-implantitis, they have a number of side effects, including insufficient concentrations at

the site that do not exceed the microorganisms' Biofilm inhibitory concentration (BIC) and hepatorenal toxicity. As a result, antibiotics must be released locally at the implant site. One technique for preventing peri-implant infections is implant surface manufacturing or the integration of antibiotics onto the implant surfaces.8 Inhibition of bacterial adhesion and growth is linked to sustained and high concentrations of medications that fulfil the pathogenic microorganisms' Biofilm inhibitory concentration (BIC) [8,9].

Drug Delivery System

A drug delivery system (DDS) is a formulation or a device that regulates the rate, timing, and site of drug release in the body to enhance the effectiveness and safety of a medicinal material when it is introduced into the body [10]. The primary goal of drug release is to prevent infections and bacterial load at the implant site. However, if the drug is released too rapidly, there is a risk of infection since the whole drug has drained from the scaffold in the first few minutes. If drug release is delayed too long, infection can spread even deeper, making wound healing more difficult to manage. As a result, superior drug release choices would include increased antibiotic release at the start and continuous release at an effective rate to effectively reduce the risk of infection from bacteria in the scaffold [10].

Local DDSs in bone might help with regeneration, infection prevention, and post-surgical pain relief. For long-term drug release, DDS for drug eluting dental implants (DEIs) has been

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produced with a considerable antibacterial or bone regeneration impact.

Implant coatings have given rise to the idea of implants as drug carriers. The term “Drug Carriers” was coined in 1988 to describe forms into which chemicals are inserted to improve drug delivery and efficacy [11]. Drug carriers are components of drug-delivery systems that can improve targeted drug delivery, efficiency, and reduce the drug’s systemic effects and metabolism. Micro/nano spheres, nanofiber, nano capsule, and hydrogel dendrimer are some of the drug carriers.

One major reason for changing the surface of dental implants is to speed up the osseointegration process [12]. The part of a dental implant that is in touch with environment is the surface, and the surface’s uniqueness drives the reaction and influences the mechanical strength of the implant/tissue interface. DEIs enhances bone apposition and increase surface area for implant bone interface, allowing stress to be efficiently conveyed and controlled in cultured osteoblasts. Examples include mechanical treatments like machining and grit blasting, chemical treatments like acid etching, electrochemical treatments like anodic oxidation, vacuum treatments, thermal treatments, and laser treatments [12].

Types of Drug Delivery Systems

Based on the mechanism of action: The release of therapeutic substances around DEIs physical surroundings is mediated by four different mechanisms [12].

1. Diffusion-controlled: Reservoirs & Matrices
2. Solvent-controlled
3. Chemical controlled (such as polymer degradation), and
4. pH-sensitivity.

Bioactive Materials as Implant Coatings

Numerous coating materials, such as silica, hydroxyapatite, carbon, bisphosphonates, calcium phosphates, titanium, fluoride, and bioactive glasses, have been investigated for dental implants [13].

With its customizable particle size, porous structure, and ease of adhesion to any surface, silica is an appealing material. Because of these qualities, silica is an impressive substance that may be used for coatings among other things. Despite the fact that pure silica is non-antibacterial, its vast surface area and adaptable structure allow it to be employed as a carrier for antibacterial metal ions and medicines in dental applications [14, 15].

Calcium phosphate coating material, which is chemically identical to bones and teeth, was developed combining high strength of metal with the bioactivity of calcium phosphate compound [16]. Calcium phosphate cements (CPC), beta-tricalciumphosphate, and hydroxyapatite are all calcium phosphate compounds (HA). Calcium phosphate breaks down, leaving calcium and phosphate (Ca^{2+} , PO_4^{3-}) as end products that are biocompatible, bioactive, and promote new bone growth. Their ability to induce osteoconduction and osseointegration, as well as their biocompatibility and nontoxicity of their chemical components are all important factors. Body fluids can exchange surface ions with aqueous solution when calcium phosphate is in touch with them, or other ions and molecules, such collagen and proteins, can be adsorbed onto the surface [17, 18]. The major goal of employing CPC as coating is to create a quick and robust biological bond with bone. Wet chemical precipitation can produce HA nanoparticles, which have a good bactericidal impact on implant-related infections due to the toxic

effect of destroying the bacterial membrane [19].

When compared to titanium surfaces, CPC surfaces bind more attachment proteins, including as fibronectin and vitronectin, for the integrin-mediated binding action of osteoprogenitors [20]. Surface form influences osseointegration, and calcium phosphate is osteoconductive. In a few animal studies, calcium phosphate has been shown to promote BIC and peri-implant bone development. Early loading, more crestal bone retention, and reduced pocket development are all advantages of calcium phosphate coated dental implants, according to the study, leading in superior long-term survival rates. Calcium phosphate coatings have been proven to increase the surface roughness of implants in vivo tests. Coated implants have been shown to have a higher chance of failure due to peri-implant illnesses than non-coated implants. Coatings may separate from the substructure, dissolve in tissue fluids, be susceptible to bacterial colonization, and/or result in rapid osseous breakdown around the implant, and cause peri-implantitis, and implant failure because of their roughness and hydrophilicity.

When calcium phosphate coated and non-coated implants were tracked for a period of three to six months, no unfavourable periodontal reactions were seen. Silver, titanium dioxide, and hydroxyapatite were used in a dual-layered nanocoating developed by Besinis et al [21]. Yang et al. demonstrated an antibacterial PLGA($\text{Ag-Fe}_3\text{O}_4$)-coated dental implant that also promoted osteoblast growth [22].

Metals as Antimicrobial Coatings

Silver, zinc, and copper are the most commonly used metallic agents that are biocidal, bactericidal, and bacteriostatic. They are highly effective at killing a wide range of pathogens through contact killing, and when used in a controlled concentration, they do not pose any health risks. Non-metallic materials, such as nanodiamond, have also been described for their bioactive and bactericidal potential in implant coatings [23].

Antibiotics as Implant Coatings

Implant antibiotic coatings have been investigated as a potential tactic to stop infection from migrating to the surgical site. There has been recent reporting of a dual-function DDS with antibacterial and bone-regeneration capabilities. Covalent conjugation was used to introduce antibacterial peptides, chlorhexidine, and antibiotics like doxycycline and tetracycline into dental implants. Nanoparticles, which are commonly utilised in the production of DDS, were also used to coat dental implants [24]. The most common metal ions employed in the coating are zinc oxide and silver nanoparticles [24]. Other bioactive nanomaterials, including gelatin, chitosan, and hydroxylapatite, in biodegradable / bioactive form can be coated with dental implants as carriers to aid bone regeneration [25].

- Cationic antibacterial agents
- Bioactive antibacterial agents

Tetracyclines have been shown in studies to promote fibroblastic cell proliferation and decrease collagenase activity, in addition to being an efficient broad-spectrum antibiotic against periodontitis and peri-implantitis-associated bacteria (e.g., Pg, Fn, Pi, and Aa). Tetracycline-containing fibres coated titanium implants - Pg, Fn, Pi, Aa - inhibited biofilm formation and continued to release for three days [26]. The antibacterial activity of a titanium implant coated with silica and gentamycin was demonstrated after 14 days after discharge [26]. Titanium implant coated with tetracycline-loaded nanofibers - Aa, Fn, Pg, Pi It had an antibacterial action. Tetracycline-loaded titanium-Pg demonstrated antibacterial efficacy and 15-day

release. The implant's surface can be coated with hydroxyapatite, gentamicin, and other systemic antibiotics before surgery implantation of the device.

In orthopaedics and dentistry, dual drug eluting titanium substrates such as Gentamicin sulphate and/or bone morphogenic protein-2 (BMP-2) coated titanium are potential materials for improved osteointegration and longevity of implant [27].

Antimicrobial peptides from human body defence are being synthesised or mimicked, ushering in a new era of diminishing antimicrobial resistance and antibiotic resistance. AMPs are produced from human proteins and have wide antibacterial, antiviral, and antifungal properties. They are covalently bound or physically adsorbed on the surface of implants [28].

Bisphosphonates as implant coatings

Bisphosphonates are a type of anti-osteoporosis drug [29]. Bisphosphonates have been connected to BRONJ (bisphosphonate-related osteonecrosis of the jaws), however when administered topically, they have been found to promote periodontal health and bone formation. Bisphosphonates inhibit osteoclasts and hence diminish bone resorption by blocking the farnesyl diphosphate synthase (FPPS) enzyme in the HMG-CoA reductase pathway. Bisphosphonates are selective in their actions, preferring to interact with bone cells over other tissues [30-32]. Because of their anti-resorptive qualities, bisphosphonates have been immobilised on the surface of titanium dental implants. It has also been suggested that such coatings aid in the formation of new bone around dental implants [33]. In contrast, some studies have found no difference between Bisphosphonate-releasing implants, HA-coated implants, and uncoated implants [20]. Bisphosphonates have been coated on the surface of dental implants using a variety of processes, including sprayed plasma coatings, fibrinogen, anodization, and heat treatment, as well as immobilisation on porous surfaces [34-36].

Dual-functional dental implants containing a combination of low-molecular-weight quaternized polyethyleneimine and alendronate covalently conjugated onto PGED brushes inhibited bacterial infection early on and improved osteointegration and biomechanical properties between the implants and bone tissues later on [37].

Chlorhexidine

Diniz and colleagues developed a hydrogel loaded with silver lactate that can help induce the osteogenic differentiation of human bone

marrow and gingival mesenchymal stem cells. It can also significantly inhibit *A. actinomycetemcomitans* by releasing silver ions for 2 weeks [38]. The antibacterial action of chlorhexidine hexametaphosphate nanoparticles coated titanium - Sg was proven, as was the persistent release of soluble chlorhexidine over 99 days [39].

The PIXIT implant, which contains polysiloxane oligomers and chlorhexidine gluconate, regulated bacterial adherence and reduced the number of bacterial species linked to long-term dental implant failure. The dental implant saliva-derived biofilm was covered with Dimethylaminododecyl Methacrylate (DMADDM), which prevented biofilm formation and regulated the microecosystem [40, 41]. Antibacterial agents that are bioactive Sg titanium implant coated with chitosan/P-HAP bilayers A proper mouse pre-osteoblastic cell response was demonstrated, as well as substantial antibacterial action [42].

Antimicrobial peptides as implant coatings

Antimicrobial peptides (AMPs), which are active against a wide spectrum of (antibiotic-resistant) planktonic bacteria and biofilms, are being eyed as antimicrobial coating candidates. Bacteria are also less prone to develop resistance to these fast-acting peptides. Antimicrobial peptide GL13K, generated from parotid secretory protein, has been examined in vitro and in vivo and found to be efficient as antimicrobial surface coatings. It has previously been proven to be bactericidal and bacteriostatic [43,44].

Limitations of drug coatings

Though the concept of drug coatings is new and appears promising, (Table 1) there are some concerns about it. These include insufficient drug release over longer periods of time, which may not reach the minimum inhibitory concentration, the development of bacterial resistance, and low coating bonding strength, which may lead to coating displacement, affecting implant osseointegration. Furthermore, the existence of a complicated implant design with sharp threads may cause stress concentration, resulting in implant coating dislodgment [45].

Conclusion

Dental implants with integrated antibacterial properties are becoming more and more common as a means of lowering the risk of infection because bacterial infection is the main cause of dental implant failure. Antibacterial and bioactive coatings are recommended to help prevent implant failure due to infection and

Table 1: Surface coatings materials used as DEIs

Type of Coating	Composition	Evidence
Bio active implant coatings	Silica	Zhang J[14], Massa MA[15]
	Calcium phosphate	Wu TY[16], Bohner M[17], Wu T[18], Denissen H[20]
	Hydroxyapatite	Chen WC[19], Besinis A[21]
	PLGA	Yang, Y[22]
	Chitosan	Xie XH[25], Escobar A[42]
Metals	Dimethyl Methacrylate	Li B[41]
	Silver, Zinc	Chen WC[19], Najeeb S[23], Carvajal JC[24]
	Tetracycline	Baskar K[26]
Antimicrobials	Gentamycin	Lee DW[27]
	Antimicrobial Peptides	Khurshid Z[28], Holmberg KV[43], Chen X[44]
	Bisphosphonates	Pradeep A[30], Sharma A[31], Leu C[32], Abtahi J[33], Denissen H[20]
	Chlorhexidine Gluconate	Diniz IM[38], Wood NJ[39]

inflammation. The osseo-conductivity of coatings has to be confirmed by more in vitro and clinical trials, despite data indicating that DEIs improve implant stability and osseointegration.

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